

EIA- An Essential Planning Tool to Make Development Initiatives Sustainable

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Abstract: *The world around us is changing at a severe rate. The developing country that is the south part is not far behind in the competition of development and economic growth. The developed countries, the north part is still clutching all the progress they can get. But such progress is not escorted with environmental stability. The environment includes all the all living and non-living things that occur naturally on Earth. Any kind of new action can and may create a re action on the environment .excess progressive projects of the last several hundreds of years has caused various adverse impacts on the ecosystem. Therefore it is vital to assess the baseline situation or the present situation of the environment without the project, to measure the all the possible impact of the project on the environment. Hence an Environment Impact Assessment (EIA) should be the fundamental planning instrument; it must be used on that particular project before the work is started. Progress is a desired status but if it is accompanied with a sustainable development .EIA is just the tool to help with that agenda.*

Date of Submission: 20-11-2024

Date of Acceptance: 21-12-2024

Introduction

In recent years the change in the ecosystem has become an issue of global concern. The widespread social economic factors are encouraging exploitative development, while giving less and less importance to the sustainable use of the resources. Development is necessary the in this competitive world. Regrettably most of such developments are done on the cost of exploitation of the environment and the ecosystem. Hence such enhancements that disregard the danger on the nature can be seen as threat to the environment. We need a tool that will give progress through sustainable development.

Literature review

Sustainable development: According to the World Commission on Environment and Development in 1987, (Brundtland Commission 1987) .Sustainable le development is defined as the development that meets the present need without compromising the future generation’s ability to fulfill their own wants.

The sustainable use of the environmental resources means, the natural resources are used in an efficient way, within their carrying capacity. It also refers prevention of any kind environmental degradation. Such degradation may cause loss of biodiversity, extinction of various species, climate change, desertification, deforestation, various natural catastrophes. In simple words, any unplanned development projects may damage the natural custom of the environment .such calamities are lead

by various unsuitable development project, that overlooks the side effects of this project. The project may deliver economic growth but at the cost of environmental deterioration. Thus these projects cause various unwanted impacts on not only the environmental resources but also on ecosystem, human health and biodiversity. The main challenges that sustainable development faces are the uncontrolled human activity. At the present scenario human activities are consuming about 40% of the net productivity total land. In the world almost 60% of the total world population is below the poverty level. On top of that the number of population is increasing day by day. Because of such severe situation our environment has been affected in various ways.

Discussion

Impacts on the environments:

A major impact of unsustainable development is environmental degradation. The term simply describes the deterioration of the environment through depletion of natural resources-air, water, soil, destruction of ecosystem, the extinction of various species and wildlife, loss of biodiversity, global warming, desertification, drainage of wetland etc. environmental degradation can occur naturally but because of the last several years of unlimited industrial development, human actions can be considered as a main root of environmental degradation.

There are many kinds of degradation such as loss of rain forests, acid rain, ozone depletion, air pollution etc. the excess use of renewable and non renewable fossil fuel is the main cause of the ozone depletion and acid rain. The air pollution, water pollution and deforestation are mainly caused by unsustainable development in the world.

EIA-environmental impact assessment-

Today the world is in need of a development process that meets the goal of growth as well as the sustainable use and preservation of the nature. EIA is such a process. EIA or the environmental impact assessment is a process that identifies, predicts, evaluates and mitigates the social, biological, and all the relevant effects of any proposed development project, prior to any major decision being taken. According to Mann in 1979, EIA is a process to identify and predict the impact on the environment and on man's health and well being of legislative proposals, policies, projects and to interpret and communicate about the impacts.

How EIA helps to preserve, conserve the natural resources -

The definition of EIA explains that this process aims to provide a better assessment for any proposed projects and points out the probable impacts on the environment.

- The main objective of EIA is to inform the decision makers about the probable impacts on the environment. The ultimate goal of this process is to promote sustainable development.
- It ensures sustainable development by making certain that the projects don't undermine critical resources and ecological functions or the wellbeing of animals and people who depend on them.
- Identify appropriate measures for mitigating the probable impacts.
- Facilitate to inform decision making providing suitable environmental terms and conditions.
- The long term aim of EIA is to protect human health and safety.
- Avoid irreversible changes, serious damage of the ecosystem.

EIA-key to sustainable development

Sustainable development concept redefines the term development and the gives a fresh new meaning of the term. Development can not represent economic growth only but also must signify that such growth cannot be done at the cost of exploitation of natural resources.

Many developmental projects have been initiated with no or little botheration to the danger it might pose to the environment. The natural resources are used without thinking about the future impact. In such cases if EIA was used then the decision maker would have let known about the future impacts the initiated project may cause. EIA can reduce the burden of environmental impacts and make developmental activities sustainable. Applying EIA prior can help to minimize adverse effects on the environment. AS EIA intends to warn about the probable irreversible changes of the natural resources, the decision maker then can plan to design, construct the projects that will accumulate environmental standards and management objectives,. BY applying EIA, we can get improved development planning that is environmental friendly and also an analysis of alternatives of design.

Conclusion and Recommendations

In the modern world everyone is racing after economic growth and increased life standard. In order to achieve such goal excessive rate of industrialization and developmental projects are being initiated. All this in expense of exploitation of the natural resources as a result environmental degradation. But such devastation can be prevented if EIA is applied in prior of any developmental project is planned. EIA don't cause excessive delay in the project .EIA helps the project to be more well design and a well design project can minimize risks and impact on the environment.

Yes, some might still say that EIA is costly and it wastes valuable time. But when not applying EIA simply outcome an environmental deterioration, that cost and use of time simply becomes the most efficient trade of to do. EIA, Therefore is an essential planning tool in sustainable development. After all there is only one EARTH for us so let's be cautious and preserve it.

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